

Michael Reaction with 7-Hydroxy-3-Carboethoxycoumarin

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Michael addition of cyclic ketones, acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, ethylcyanoacetate and ethylacetoacetate to 7-hydroxy-3-carboethoxycoumarin at different conditions gives the Michael adducts(II-IX). The structures have been supported by elemental analysis and spectral data.

WE have recently¹⁻⁵ described some of the reactions of 3-carboethoxycoumarins. The present work reports the Michael reaction of 7-hydroxy-3-carboethoxycoumarin(I), in which the C₃-C₄ olefinic double bond is activated due to conjugation to both the carboethoxy and carboxyl groups.

In the presence of sodium methoxide at room temperature cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone condense with coumarin 1, and subsequent hydrolysis of the lactone ring leads to the formation of [α (2-oxocyclopentyl or 2-oxocyclohexyl)-6-hydroxy-salicyl]malonic acid (IIa and b). The infrared spectra of II showed well defined absorption bands at 1712-1745 cm⁻¹ (C=O of cyclic ketone), 1724-1758 cm⁻¹ (dicarboxylic acids) and 3122-3440 cm⁻¹ (OH).

(a) R = 2-oxocyclopentyl
(b) R = 2-oxocyclohexyl

On the other hand, at room temperature in presence of ammonium acetate cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone condense with I to give 2,7-dihydroxy-(2,3)cyclopenta (or cyclohexa) chroman-4- α -carboethoxyacetic acid (IIIa and b). Compounds III showed absorption at 1700-1748 cm⁻¹ (half ester) and 3000-3500 cm⁻¹ (OH groups).

Treatment of I and cyclic ketones at 170° in presence of ammonium acetate give 7-hydroxy-4-(2-oxocyclopentyl, or 2-oxocyclohexyl)-3N-carbamidocoumarin(IV a and b) and 7-hydroxy-1,2-cyclopent (or cyclohex)-1-ene-4-10b-dihydro-4H 1 benzopyrano-3, 4-C pyridine-4, 5 (3H)dione (Va and b). The ir spectra of (IV) showed bands at 1600 cm⁻¹ (δ lactone), 2680 cm⁻¹ (C=O primary

amide 2820-2905 cm⁻¹ (cyclic CH) and 3140-3440 cm⁻¹ (OH or NH), while compounds V showed bands at 1580 cm⁻¹ (δ lactone), 1640 cm⁻¹ (δ lactam), 2805-2900 cm⁻¹ (cyclic CH) and 3130-3448 cm⁻¹ (OH or NH).

(a) R = 2-oxocyclopentyl
(b) R = 2-oxocyclohexyl

In the presence of sodium methoxide at room temperature acetylacetone and benzoylacetone condense with (I) with subsequent hydrolysis of lactone ring leading to the formation of [α -(1-acetylacetyl or benzoyl) 6-hydroxy-salicyl]malonic acids (VIa and b). The infrared spectra of VI showed well defined absorption bands at 1618-1637 cm⁻¹ (B-diketones), 1730-1758 cm⁻¹ (dicarboxylic acids) and 3122-3580 cm⁻¹ (OH).

On the other hand, at 170° acetylacetone and benzoylacetone in the presence of sodium methoxide condense with (I) to give 3-hydroxy-10-acetyl- (or benzoyl)-6a, 7,8,9,10,10a-hexahydro-6,7,9-tri-oxo-6H-dibenzo[b,d]pyran (VIIa and b). The infrared absorption spectra of (VII) showed bands at 1550-1580 cm⁻¹ (B diketones), 1620-1640 cm⁻¹ (δ lactone), 1640 or 1720 cm⁻¹ (acetyl- or benzoyl) and 3340-3510 cm⁻¹ (OH).

(a) R = COCH₃
(b) R = COC₆H₅

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In an analogous manner(I) was found to condense with ethylacetoacetate and ethylcyanoacetate

at room temperature in presence of sodium methoxide to give 1-acetyl (or carbethoxy)-10-hydroxy-1,2,4a,10b-tetrahydro-4H,5H-pyrano [3,4-c]-[1] benzopyran-2,4,5-triones (VIIIa and b). The ir spectrum of (VIIIa) showed band at 1643 cm^{-1} (C=O acetyl), while (VIIIb) showed band at 1748 cm^{-1} (C=O of carbethoxy).

On the other hand, I condenses with ethylcyanoacetate at 170° in the presence of ammonium acetate to give two products 1-carbamido (and/or cyano) 10-hydroxy-4a, 10b-dihydro-2H, 3H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-c] pyridine-2,4,5-[1H,-3H]-triones (IXa and b). The ir spectrum of (IXa) showed band at 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O-primary amide) while (IXb) showed band at 2292 cm^{-1} (CN).

(VIII) (IX)
 (a) R = COCH₃ (a) R = COCH₃
 (b) R = CO₂C₂H₅ (b) R = CN

Experimental

The infrared absorption spectra were determined with Unicam SP 200G using KBr Wafer technique. All melting points were not corrected.

Michael condensation with (I) at room temperature in presence of sod-methoxide: A mixture of active methylene compound (0.015 mole), 7-hydroxy-3-carbethoxycoumarin (0.01 mole), and sodium methoxide (0.02 mole) was kept at room temperature for 3 days. The reaction mixture was poured on dilute hydrochloric acid (100 ml 2%). The solid product separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from the proper solvent.

Michael condensation with (I) at 170° in presence of sodium methoxide: The same procedure as above was done at 170° for 3 hrs.

Michael condensation with (I) at room temperature in the presence of ammonium acetate: A mixture of coumarin(I) (0.01 mole), active methylene compounds (0.015 mole) and ammonium acetate (0.03 mole) was treated with enough ethanol to make a homogeneous phase. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 days and then heated on steam bath for 1 hr with vigorous stirring. The solution was evaporated to a syrup, stirred with conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml), then with water (50 ml) and allowed to stand for several hrs. The solid products which separated were crystallized from the suitable solvents.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS II-IX

Comp.	Method	m.p.	Solvent (Yield%)	Formula (Mol. Wt.)	Analysis%	
					Calcd.	Found
IIa	a	242	dil. E (68)	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₇ (308)	C, 58.44 H, 5.19	58.67 5.24
IIb	a	265	E (78)	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₇ (324)	C, 59.68 H, 5.59	59.82 5.47
IIIa	c	155	M (51)	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₇ (336)	C, 60.71 H, 5.96	60.59 5.87
IIIb	c	165	M (53)	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₇ (350)	C, 61.71 H, 6.29	61.82 6.37
IVa	d	232	A (58)	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₆ (301)	C, 63.79 H, 4.98 N, 4.65	63.56 4.87 4.74
IVb	d	255	A (61)	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₆ (315)	C, 64.76 H, 5.40 N, 4.44	64.66 5.32 4.37
Va	d	300	X (54)	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₆ (288)	C, 67.84 H, 4.59 N, 4.95	67.68 4.48 4.88
Vb	d	300	X (59)	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₆ (297)	C, 68.69 H, 5.05 N, 4.71	68.54 5.01 4.62
VIa	a	257	E (52)	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆ (324)	C, 55.56 H, 4.94	55.63 4.87
VIb	a	255	E (57)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₆ (386)	C, 62.18 H, 4.66	62.23 4.54
VIIa	b	175	X (48)	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₆ (288)	C, 62.50 H, 4.17	62.63 4.23
VIIb	b	188	X (51)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₆ (350)	C, 68.57 H, 4.00	68.71 4.04
VIIIa	a	258	M (72)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇ (290)	C, 57.93 H, 3.45	57.84 3.51
VIIIb	a	261	E (68)	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₆ (320)	C, 56.25 H, 3.75	56.31 3.68
IXa	d	264	E (32)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ (290)	C, 53.79 H, 3.45 N, 9.66	53.68 3.51 9.54
IXb	d	292	A (4)	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ O ₆ (272)	C, 57.35 H, 2.94 N, 10.29	57.49 2.97 10.34

A : Acetic acid ; E : Ethanol ; M : Methanol ; X : Xylene.

Michael condensation with (I) at 170° in the presence of ammonium acetate: A mixture of coumarin(I) (0.01 mole), active methylene compounds (0.01 mole) and ammonium acetate (0.03 mole), was heated in a sealed tube at 170° for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was stirred with conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml), washed with water, dried and crystallized from the proper solvent.

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